

Global Stability of an HIV Dynamical Model with Crowley-Martin Functional Response

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Abstract

Mathematical modeling is an important method to study and research for the dynamic of viral infection in mathematical biology. The aim of this article is to study the global dynamic of HIV virus infection model with Crowley-Martin functional response and give the results by using Lyapunov's second method and LaSalle's invariance principle. We derive the basic reproduction number R_0 and prove the global stability of rest points of system when $R_0 \leq 1$, $R_0 > 1$, respectively.

Keywords: Viral infection; Global stability; Crowley-Martin; Lyapunov function

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1. Introduction

Recently, there has been much interest in mathematical modeling of viral infection dynamics (see [11, 12]). The basic viral infection model in [10] has the following form:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dT}{dt} = s - dT - \beta TV, \\ \frac{dI}{dt} = \beta TV - \delta I, \\ \frac{dV}{dt} = pI - cV, \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

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where $T(0) = T_0, I(0) = I_0$ and $V(0) = V_0$ are given, which has been widely used for studying the dynamic behavior of infections such as hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV) and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). In system (1.1), first equation shows the dynamic of uninfected cells or $CD4^+$ T helper cells. These cells (T) are produced at a constant rate s , die at a rate dT and infected with a rate βTV . The second equation of system (1.1), represents the dynamic of infected T helper cell (I). Infected $CD4^+$ T helper cells are generated by rate βTV and die at a rate δI . Third equation of system (1.1), describes the dynamic of virus particles (V). These virus particles are released from infected cells at a rate pI and die at a rate cV . In system (1.1) the rate of infection is bilinear. However, the actual incidence rate is not linear. Recently, many studies have been done to improve this basic model by changing the incidence rate according to different background (see [1-17] and reference cited therein). In this paper, the incidence rate of HIV is given by Crowley-Martin functional response, $\frac{\beta TV}{1+aT+bV+abTV}$, where $a, b > 0$, which was introduced by Crowley and Martin [1]. When $a > 0, b = 0$, the Crowley-Martin functional response is simplified to Michaelis-Menten or Holling type II functional response in [6]. On the other hand, if $a = 0, b > 0$, it expresses a saturate response in Song and Neumann [14]. And when $a = 0$ and $b = 0$, Crowley-Martin functional response is reduced to Holing type I.

In this paper, the following system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dT}{dt} = s - dT - \frac{\beta TV}{1+aT+bV+abTV}, \\ \frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{\beta TV}{1+aT+bV+abTV} - \delta I, \\ \frac{dV}{dt} = pI - cV, \end{cases} \tag{1.2}$$

will be studied and some sufficient conditions will be given about the global stability of critical points of system (1.2).

In [15], authors gave the following theorem for the global stability of positive equilibrium of system (1.2).

Theorem 1.1. *Suppose that*

- (i) $R_0 > 1$;
- (ii) $c\delta \left(\frac{\beta V_* + b\beta V_*^2}{(1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*)^2} + d \right) > \frac{dp(\beta T_* + b\beta T_*^2)}{(1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*)^2}$;
- (iii) $\left(c + d + \delta + \frac{\beta V_* + b\beta V_*^2}{(1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*)^2} \right) \times \left[cd + d\delta + (c + \delta) \frac{\beta V_* + b\beta V_*^2}{(1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*)^2} \right] + (c + \delta)c\delta > p \left(c + \delta + 2dp + \frac{\beta V_* + b\beta V_*^2}{(1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*)^2} \right) \frac{\beta T_* + b\beta T_*^2}{(1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*)^2}$;
- (iv) $d > \frac{as\delta}{d}$.

Then the positive equilibrium (T_, I_*, V_*) is globally asymptotically stable.*

Remark 1.2. In Theorem 1.1, R_0 is a basic reproduction number, which will be defined in section 2.

For the global stability of positive equilibrium of (1.2), by using Lyapunov’s second method and LaSalle’s invariance principle, a sufficient condition will be stated, which improves the results in [15]. Our results are very simple and only depend on the value of R_0 . In section 2, some auxiliary results will be given. In section 3, we will find the equilibriums of system (1.2) and will study the global dynamic of these points.

2. Basic results

In this section, the positivity and boundedness of solution of (1.2) will be stated. Since the model (1.2) represents the growth of a cell population, these cells should persist non-negative and bounded. Thus, the following theorem which is proved in [5] can be stated.

Theorem 2.1. *All solutions starting from non-negative initial conditions exist for all $t > 0$ and remain bounded and non-negative. Moreover, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} M(t) &\leq M(0) + \frac{s}{\delta} \\ V(t) &\leq V_0 + \frac{p}{c} \|I\|_{\infty}, \end{aligned}$$

where $M = T + I$ represents the total cells of uninfected and infected cells, and $\delta = \min\{a, d\}$.

To state our main results, the following definition will be needed.

Definition 2.2. In epidemiology, the basic reproduction number, R_0 is defined as the expected number of secondary infections produced by an index case in a completely susceptible population.

This number is a measure of the potential for disease spread within a population. If $R_0 < 1$, then a few infected individuals introduced into a completely susceptible population will, on average, fail to replace themselves, and the disease will not spread. If, on the other hand, $R_0 > 1$, then the number of infected individuals will increase with each generation and the disease will spread. For system (1.2), from [5], it can be concluded that the basic reproduction number is as follows:

$$R_0 = \frac{sp\beta}{\delta c(d + sa)}.$$

In the next section, we will obtain the global stability of equilibrium points of system (1.2) by the value of R_0 .

3. Global stability

In this section, global stability of system (1.2) will be studied. First, we find the equilibriums of system (1.2). If $V = 0$, from second equation of the model, it can be obtained that $I = 0$. By the first equation, we must have $T = \frac{s}{d}$. Thus, $E_0 = (T_0, 0, 0) = (\frac{s}{d}, 0, 0)$ is a disease-free equilibrium or uninfected steady state equilibrium of system (1.2). This equilibrium states that the viruses are absent. Hence, the system (1.2) has a unique disease-free equilibrium $E_0 = (T_0, 0, 0)$ if $R_0 \leq 1$. The following theorem which is proved in [15], gives a sufficient condition about the existence of the positive equilibrium or endemic equilibrium of system (1.2) if $R_0 > 1$.

Theorem 3.1. *If $R_0 > 1$, then system (1.2) has a unique positive equilibrium $E_* = (T_*, I_*, V_*)$, where T_*, I_* and V_* are*

$$\begin{aligned} T_* &= \frac{-(p\beta - \delta ca + bpd - absp)}{2abpd} + \frac{\sqrt{(p\beta - \delta ca + bpd - absp)^2 + 4abpd(\delta s + bps)}}{2abpd}, \\ I_* &= \frac{1}{\delta}(s - dT_*), \\ V_* &= \frac{p}{c}I_*. \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to check that if $R_0 > 1$, then $s - dT_* > 0$. Hence, system (1.2) has a unique positive equilibrium or endemic equilibrium $E_* = (T_*, I_*, V_*)$, if $R_0 > 1$. The endemic equilibrium states that the viruses are present.

In the following, the global asymptotically stabilities of these two equilibria will be given.

Theorem 3.2. *If $R_0 \leq 1$, then the disease-free equilibrium E_0 is globally asymptotically stable.*

Proof. Define a Lyapunov function

$$L_0(T, I, V) = \frac{1}{1 + aT_0} \left(T - T_0 - T_0 \ln \frac{T}{T_0} \right) + I + \frac{\delta}{p} V.$$

Its derivative along solutions of system (1.2) can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_0}{dt} |_{(1.2)} &= \frac{1}{1 + aT_0} \dot{T} - \frac{1}{1 + aT_0} \frac{T_0}{T} \dot{T} + \dot{I} + \frac{\delta}{p} \dot{V} \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + aT_0} \left(s - dT - \frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} \right) - \frac{1}{1 + aT_0} \frac{T_0}{T} \left(s - dT - \frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} - \delta I + \frac{\delta}{p} (pI - cV). \end{aligned}$$

Note that $T_0 = \frac{s}{d}$ and $R_0 = \frac{sp\beta}{\delta c(d+sa)}$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_0}{dt} |_{(1.2)} &= \frac{dT_0}{1 + aT_0} \left(2 - \frac{T}{T_0} - \frac{T_0}{T} \right) + \frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} + \frac{1}{1 + aT_0} \frac{\beta T_0 V}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{1 + aT_0} \frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} - \frac{\delta cV}{p} \\ &= \frac{dT_0}{1 + aT_0} \left(2 - \frac{T}{T_0} - \frac{T_0}{T} \right) + \frac{\delta cV(1 + aT)}{p(1 + aT + bV + abTV)} (R_0 - 1) \\ &\quad - \frac{\delta cV(V + aT)}{p(1 + aT + bV + abTV)}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $2 - \frac{T}{T_0} - \frac{T_0}{T} \leq 0$ and $R_0 \leq 1$, we have that $\frac{dL_0}{dt} \leq 0$ for all $T, I, V > 0$. Hence, the disease-free equilibrium E_0 is stable. On the other hand, $\frac{dL_0}{dt} = 0$ if and only if $T = T_0$ and $I = V = 0$. Let M be the largest invariant set in

$$D = \{(T, I, V) \mid \dot{L}_0(T, I, V) = 0\} = \{E_0\}.$$

We have that $M = \{E_0\}$. The global stability of E_0 follows from LaSalle’s invariance principle [3, 4]. □

From Theorem 3.2 it can be concluded that, if one virus produce one or less than one virus during its lifetime ($R_0 \leq 1$), the virus cannot attack and will soon be cleared.

In the following, we study the global stability of endemic equilibrium of system (1.2).

Theorem 3.3. *If $R_0 > 1$, then the endemic equilibrium E_* is globally asymptotically stable.*

Proof. Define a Lyapunov function

$$L_*(T, I, V) = T - T_* - \int_{T_*}^T \frac{\delta I_*}{\frac{\beta \eta V_*}{1 + a\eta + bV_* + ab\eta V_*}} d\eta + I - I_* - I_* \ln \frac{I}{I_*} + \frac{\delta}{p} \left(V - V_* - V_* \ln \frac{V}{V_*} \right).$$

The function $L_*(T, I, V)$ is positive definite with respect to $(T - T_*, I - I_*, V - V_*)$. The time derivative of $L_*(T, I, V)$ along the positive solutions of system (1.2) can be written as follow.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_*}{dt} |_{(1.2)} &= \dot{T} - \delta I_* \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{\beta TV_*} \dot{T} + \dot{I} - \frac{I_*}{I} \dot{I} + \frac{\delta}{p} \left(\dot{V} - \frac{V_*}{V} \dot{V} \right) \\ &= s - dT - \delta I_* \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{\beta TV_*} \left(s - dT - \frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{I_*}{I} \left(\frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} - \delta I \right) - \frac{\delta cV}{p} - \frac{\delta V_*}{pV} (pI - cV). \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

From the model, we have

$$s = dT_* + \delta I_*, \quad \frac{\delta c}{p} = \frac{\delta I_*}{V_*}, \quad \delta I_* = \frac{\beta T_* V_*}{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_* V_*}. \tag{3.2}$$

Thus,

$$s - dT - \frac{\delta cV}{p} = dT_* + \delta I_* - dT - \frac{\delta I_* V}{V_*}, \tag{3.3}$$

therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} & -\delta I_* \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{\beta TV_*} \left(s - dT - \frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} \right) \\ &= -\frac{T_*}{T} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*} (dT_* + \delta I_* - dT) + \delta I_* \frac{V}{V_*} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT + bV + abTV}, \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

and

$$-\frac{I_*}{I} \left(\frac{\beta TV}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} - \delta I \right) = -\delta I_* \frac{I_* TV}{IT_* V_*} \frac{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} + \delta I_*. \tag{3.5}$$

From (3.2)-(3.5), it can be obtained that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_*}{dt} |_{(1.2)} &= dT_* \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_*} - \frac{T_*}{T} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*} + \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*} \right) \\ &+ \delta I_* \left(1 - \frac{T_*}{T} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*} + \frac{V}{V_*} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} \right) \\ &+ \delta I_* \left(1 - \frac{I_* TV}{IT_* V_*} \frac{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} \right) + \delta I_* \left(1 - \frac{V}{V_*} - \frac{V_* I}{I_* V} \right) \\ &= -\frac{d(1 + bV_*)}{T(1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*)} (T - T_*)^2 \\ &+ \delta I_* \left(-1 - \frac{V}{V_*} + \frac{V}{V_*} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} + \frac{1 + aT + bV + abTV}{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*} \right) \\ &+ \delta I_* \left(4 - \frac{T_*}{T} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*} - \frac{I_* TV}{IT_* V_*} \frac{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} - \frac{V_* I}{I_* V} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1 + aT + bV + abTV}{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \delta I_* \left(-1 - \frac{V}{V_*} + \frac{V}{V_*} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} + \frac{1 + aT + bV + abTV}{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*} \right) \\ &= -\frac{b(1 + aT)^2}{V_*(1 + aT + bV + abTV)(1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*)} (V - V_*)^2. \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

On the other hand, since the arithmetic mean is greater than or equal to the geometric mean, it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned} & 4 - \frac{T_*}{T} \frac{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*}{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*} - \frac{I_* TV}{IT_* V_*} \frac{1 + aT_* + bV_* + abT_*V_*}{1 + aT + bV + abTV} \\ & - \frac{V_* I}{I_* V} - \frac{1 + aT + bV + abTV}{1 + aT + bV_* + abTV_*} \leq 0. \end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

By (3.7) and (3.8), it can be concluded that $\frac{dL_*}{dt} \leq 0$ for all $T, I, V > 0$. Hence, the endemic equilibrium E_* is stable. On the other hand, $\frac{dL_*}{dt} = 0$ if and only if $T = T_*, I = I_*, V = V_*$. Let M be the largest invariant set in

$$D = \{(T, I, V) \mid \dot{L}_*(T, I, V) = 0\} = \{E_*\}.$$

We have that $M = \{E_*\}$. The global stability of E_* follows from LaSalle’s invariance principle [3, 4]. □

From Theorem 3.3 it can be concluded that, if one virus produce greater than one virus during its lifespan ($R_0 > 1$), the virus can invade and will soon be able to spread in T cells population.

Figure 1: Solution trajectories as functions of time, tending to stable equilibrium E_0

4. Examples and Numerical Simulations

In this section, we give some numeric simulations to explain the theoretical results of previous section by using Matlab with Runge-Kutta method (ODE45). These numerical results, support theoretical results concerning the stability of equilibrium points of system (1.2) which observed in Section (3). In the following, the first example will be given.

We show the numerical simulations to observe the dynamical behavior of system (1.2) with a hypothetical values in the Table 1.

Table 1. Parameter Values used for simulation			
Parameters	Meaning	Value	References
s	Birth rate of host cells	10	[17]
d	Decay rate of healthy cells	0.0112	Assumed
β	Viral infectivity rate	0.012,0.15	Assumed
a	Positive parameter that describe the effects of capture rate	0.00005	[17]
b	Positive parameter that describe the effects of capture rate	0.2	Assumed
δ	Death rate of infected cells, not by CTL killing	0.8	[17]
p	Virion production rate	0.12	[17]
c	Clearance rate of virus	3.5	[17]

Figure 1 shows the behavior of solutions of system (1.2) with viral infectivity rate $\beta = 0.012$ and initial values (60, 10, 2). For the parameters used in Table 1, the basic reproduction number is $\mathbf{R}_0 = 0.4396 < 1$.

In this case, the solutions of system converge to the disease-free equilibrium $E_0 = (892.8571, 0, 0)$.

Figure 2 represent the dynamic behavior the solutions of system (1.2) with viral infectivity rate $\beta = 0.15$ and initial values $(60, 10, 2)$. By this parameter, the basic reproduction number is $R_0 = 5.4945 > 1$. Hence, in this case, all the solutions tend to the endemic equilibrium $E_* = (167.7791, 10.1510, 0.3480)$.

Figure 2: Solution trajectories as functions of time, tending to stable equilibrium E_*

5. Discussion

In this paper, we considered a generalized HIV dynamical model. By constructing Lyapunov function and using LaSalle's invariance principle, we proved that the uninfected steady state E_0 and endemic steady state E_* are globally asymptotically stable when the value of the basic reproduction number R_0 satisfy certain conditions. Our results improved the results in [15] for the global stability of endemic equilibrium point.

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